

Solution of a sample of thermodynamic systems equipped with fractional stochastic operator illustrated by applications

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Abstract— Simulations play a crucial role in physics for several reasons. First, they enable the examination and analysis of complex systems and phenomena that are difficult or impossible to observe directly, such as the behavior of subatomic particles in quantum mechanics or the dynamics of galaxies in astrophysics. Second, simulations allow scientists to predict experimental results and test theories in a controlled virtual environment. In this work, our contribution is the study of certain thermodynamic phenomena in physics modeled by stochastic differential equations. This study enables us to apply stochastic approaches to simulate and estimate parameters within our equations. By combining simulations with advanced stochastic techniques, we can gain a better understanding of the dynamic behaviors of complex thermodynamic systems and improve the accuracy of our models. This integration of simulation and stochastic modeling opens new perspectives for thermodynamics research and provides powerful tools for exploring the properties of physical systems under various conditions.

Keywords— Stochastic differential equations; Ito formula; Thermodynamic system; Brownian movement; reaction-diffusion equation

1. INTRODUCTION

Differential equations have long been fundamental to physics, offering a robust framework for modeling diverse physical phenomena [3], [4]. They describe how physical quantities evolve over time and space [13], encompassing key areas such as classical mechanics, quantum mechanics, thermodynamics [18], and fluid dynamics. In classical mechanics, differential equations model the motion of particles and rigid bodies, while in electromagnetism, Maxwell's equations [12]—four partial differential equations— govern the behavior of electric and magnetic fields over time. These equations are crucial to modern electrical engineering and physics, explaining phenomena like electromagnetic waves, including visible light, radio waves, and X-rays [7]. They have not only enhanced our understanding of electromagnetic interactions but also driven technological advancements in communications, medical imaging, and other fields. In thermodynamics and statistical mechanics, differential equations are equally vital. For instance, the heat equation models how heat diffuses through materials, allowing predictions of temperature distributions essential for manufacturing and climate science. Similarly, in fluid dynamics, the Navier-Stokes equations describe fluid motion, modeling weather patterns, ocean currents, and airflow around aircraft. These equations are complex and nonlinear, often requiring advanced numerical methods and significant computational power. Mastery of fluid dynamics is crucial for various engineering disciplines, including aerospace, automotive, and environmental engineering.

Recently, stochastic differential equations have become crucial for modeling systems with uncertainty and random disturbances [1], [2], [9], and [21]. They are used in finance [10], [5], biology [8], and physics to predict complex behaviors and simulate realistic systems, benefiting from advances in numerical computation. They help in understanding stability, chaos, and phase transitions in systems ranging from electronic circuits to natural ecosystems [7]. Stochastic differential equations are vital for optimizing and controlling dynamical systems, especially under uncertainty. Techniques like Kalman filtering enhance system performance in robotics [20], automation, and energy systems. In fluid dynamics, they model pollutant dispersion, wave propagation [19], and mixing processes, making them essential for environmental impact assessments and remediation strategies. These equations extend traditional models, offering more accurate representations of complex systems in modern scientific research and engineering [16].

Our paper is organized as follows, the second section is preliminary on the main definitions and principles of fractional calculus. On the other hand, the third section is a background on Stochastic calculus tool with its principal theorems. the fourth section is a theoretical construction on the sample of the proposed equations which mixes between the fractional derivative and Brownian motion, The fifth section is a construction for the numerical solution for this sample of equations with its extensions in modern physics with applications on dynamic system samples' modelling.

2. FRACTIONAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS FIELD

Fractional calculus extends traditional calculus to non-integer orders, enabling the study of fractional derivatives and integrals. It is crucial in various fields, including physics, engineering, and finance, for modeling complex systems with memory effects or long-range interactions. This approach provides deeper insights and solutions for phenomena governed by fractional dynamics.

2.1. RIEMANN LIOUVILLE INTEGRALS

The Gamma function is essential for defining fractional derivatives.

$$\Gamma(\theta) = \int_0^{+\infty} t^{\theta-1} e^{-t} dt. \quad (1)$$

Definition 1 *Left and Right Integrals of Riemann–Liouville defined by its following formulas*

$$\mathbf{I}_{(t_0,t)}^\theta f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\theta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\theta-1} f(s) ds. \quad (2)$$

And

$$\mathbf{I}_{(t,t_0)}^\theta f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\theta)} \int_t^{t_0} (s-t)^{\theta-1} f(s) ds. \quad (3)$$

Definition 2 *Derivatives of Riemann- Liouville*

$$D_{(t_0,t)}^\theta f(t) = \frac{d^n}{dt^n} (\mathbf{I}_{(t_0,t)}^{n-\theta} f(t)) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\theta)} \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \left(\int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{n-\theta-1} f(s) ds \right). \quad (4)$$

Where $n = 1 + [\theta]$, in another side we have

$$\begin{aligned} D_{(t,t_0)}^\theta f(t) &= (-1)^n \frac{d^n}{dt^n} (\mathbf{I}_{(t,t_0)}^{n-\theta} f(t)) \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\theta)} (-1)^n \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \left(\int_t^{t_0} (s-t)^{n-\theta-1} f(s) ds \right). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

2.2 Caputo Fractional Derivatives

Caputo fractional derivatives are widely used in various fields, including physics, engineering, and applied mathematics, for modeling and analyzing systems exhibiting non-local behaviors or memory effects. They provide a powerful tool for extending classical calculus to address phenomena with fractional dynamics and are fundamental in the study of fractional differential equations.

$$D_{(t,t_0)}^{(C,\theta)} f(t) = D_{(t,t_0)}^\theta \left\{ f(t) - \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{f^{(j)}(t_0)}{j!} (t-t_0)^j \right\}. \tag{6}$$

And

$$D_{(t_0,t)}^{(C,\theta)} f(t) = D_{(t_0,t)}^\theta \left\{ f(t) - \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{f^{(j)}(t_0)}{j!} (t_0-t)^j \right\}. \tag{7}$$

2.3 Grünwald Letnikov Fractional Derivatives

Fractional calculus introduces derivatives and integrals of non-integer orders (p/q) where $(p,q) \in \mathbb{R}^+ \times \mathbb{R}^+$. The Grünwald-Letnikov definition is one way to characterize these fractional derivatives. The Grünwald-Letnikov definition is effective fractional differential formula, Where help researchers and practitioners to analyze and understand systems with fractional dynamics, providing insights into complex physical and mathematical phenomena.

Definition 3 The Grünwald-Letnikov definition noted GL , and its expression defined as follow

$$\begin{cases} u^{(\theta)}(x) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{({}^{\ominus}_h u)(x)}{h^\theta} \\ \theta > 0 \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

Where

$$({}^{\ominus}_h u)(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (-1)^j A_j^\theta u(x - jh). \tag{9}$$

Such as

$$A_j^\theta = \frac{\theta(\theta-1)(\theta-2) \times \dots \times (\theta-j+1)}{j!}. \tag{10}$$

The left-side and the right-side GL fractional derivative of order θ on finite interval $I = [a, b]$ are defined by:

$$({}^{GL} D_{a^+}^\theta u)(x) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{({}^{\ominus}_{h,a^+} u)(x)}{h^\theta}. \tag{11}$$

And

$$({}^{GL} D_{b^-}^\theta u)(x) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{({}^{\ominus}_{h,b^-} u)(x)}{h^\theta}. \tag{12}$$

Respectively, where

$$({}^{\ominus}_{h,a^+} u)(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor \frac{x-a}{h} \rfloor} (-1)^j A_j^\theta u(x - jh). \tag{13}$$

And

$$({}^{\ominus}_{h,b}u)(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{\lceil \frac{b-x}{h} \rceil} (-1)^j A_j^{\ominus} u(x + jh). \tag{14}$$

3. BACKGROUNDS ON STOCHASTIC CALCULUS TOOL

This section reviews stochastic computation tools, focusing on Brownian motion, a continuous random process first observed by Robert Brown in 1828. It models irregular particle trajectories, stock prices, thermal noise, and system disturbances, with Einstein enhancing its mathematical framework by connecting it to the heat equation and Gaussian density.

Definition 4 We recall in stochastic calculus that $w(t)$ is called standard Brownian motion, it satisfies the following conditions:

- a) $w(t)$ is almost surely continuous in t .
- b) $w(t)$ has independent increments see [12].
- c) $w(t) - w(s)$ has independent increments. obeys the normal distribution with zero mean and variance $t - s$.
- d) $w(0) = 0$.

Example 1(see [15])

$$w(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sqrt{2} \varepsilon_k \frac{\sin\{(k - 0.5)\pi t\}}{(k - 0.5)\pi}. \tag{15}$$

There are fundamental properties that characterize Brownian motion that must be applied from the simulation section and among these properties we have

$$w\left(\frac{T+1}{N}\right) - w\left(\frac{T}{N}\right) = \frac{\varepsilon_i}{\sqrt{N}}. \tag{16}$$

Such as ε_i represents independent standard Gaussian random variables.

$$d_{(0,t)}x(t) = \beta(t)x(t)d_{(0,t)}w(t).$$

Then

$$\int \frac{dx(t)}{x(t)} = \int \beta(t)dw(t).$$

Which shows that the solution is

$$x(t) = \exp\left\{\int \beta(t)dw(t)\right\} + c.$$

We assume $g : [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuously differentiable, with We define

$$\int_0^T g dw(t) = -\int_0^T g'(t)w(t)dt. \tag{17}$$

This expression can be shown using integration by parts and the PWZ expression from Paley, Wiener, and Zygmund. By representing Brownian motion, we can solve the fractional stochastic differential equation, offering realistic simulations for complex phenomena described by such equations.

2.4 Discretization

Let the standard Brownian motion $w = (w_t)_{t \in \mathbb{R}_+}$. The objective is to simulate this process in order to discretize the time interval $[0, T]$. By selecting the discretization step

$$\Delta t = T / N, \text{ for } N \in \mathbb{N}^*. \quad (18)$$

A realization of the process is simulated using the following expression.

$$\Delta t = \frac{T}{N} \Rightarrow N \Delta t = T. \quad (19)$$

Let be a realization of the vector $(w_{\Delta t}, w_{2\Delta t}, \dots, w_{N\Delta t})$. We will then approximate the trajectory of the motion $w(t)$ from this realization. Simulations are essential in physics for several reasons. They allow studying complex phenomena, predicting outcomes, and testing theories in virtual environments, offering a safe, cost-effective alternative for exploring impractical scenarios and enhancing interdisciplinary collaboration and education.

2.5 Euler Method

Difference $(w_{(k+1)\Delta t} - w_{k\Delta t})_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a sequence of independent centred Gaussian random variables with variance δ according to the definition of Brownian motion $(w_t)_{t \in \mathbb{R}_+}$. Moreover, for all $m \in \mathbb{N}^*$

$$w_{m\Delta t} = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} (w_{(k+1)\Delta t} - w_{k\Delta t}). \quad (20)$$

First step: Generate N random variables of z_k which follow from the $N(0,1)$.

Second step: we pose $w_0 = 0$, then

$$B_{k\Delta t} = B_{(k-1)\Delta t} + \sqrt{\Delta t} z_k \text{ for } k \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (21)$$

2.6 Ito's formula

Suppose $X(\cdot)$ is a real-valued stochastic process

$$X(r) = X(s) + \int_s^r F dt + \int_s^r G dw. \quad (22)$$

Such as $F \in L^1(0, T)$ and $G \in L^2(0, T)$ in domain $0 \leq s \leq r \leq T$. $X(\cdot)$ is considered a stochastic differential equation if

$$\begin{cases} dX = Fdt + Gdw \\ 0 \leq t \leq T \end{cases}. \quad (23)$$

$u : \mathbb{R} \times [0; T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, the functions $\frac{\partial u}{\partial t}, \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}$ are existent and continuous u is continuously differentiable with temps t , and twice continuously differentiable in x . We set $Y(t) = u(x(t), t)$, therefore

$$\begin{aligned} dY &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} dt + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} dX + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} dt G^2 dt \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} F + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} G^2 \right) dt + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} G dw \end{aligned}. \quad (24)$$

We call (24) Ito's formula see [6], [14]. The following Lemma focuses on presenting essential conditions required to ensure the existence and uniqueness of a solution to a stochastic differential

equation. We will then extend these conditions to stochastic differential equations involving a fractional derivative operator, beginning with a review of the probabilistic space. (Ω, A, P) generated by the tribe, provided by the probability measure, we start with the following lemma.

Lemma 1

Let the process $(x(t))_{t \in [0, M]}$ in a probabilistic space (Ω, A, P) with expression (24) such that $w(t)$ is the Brownian motion, g and h are two measurable functions on the interval $[t, M]$, and these functions are verified under the following conditions. There exists a constant $C > 0$ such that

Condition 1 : $|g(t, x(t)) - g(t, y(t))| + |h(t, x(t)) - h(t, y(t))| \leq C |x(t) - y(t)|$.

Condition 2 : $|g(t, x(t))|^2 + |h(t, x(t))|^2 \leq C^2(1 + x^2(t))$.

Then, So the equation accepts a unique solution

Proof. See [4].

Let $(w_t)_{t \in [0, T]}$ a Brownian motion defined on (Ω, F, P) , There are many methods in the probability literature to approximate the solution of stochastic differential equations,

$$\begin{cases} dX_t = \varphi_0(x, t)dt + \varphi_1(x, t)dw \\ X(0) = X_0, t \in [0, T] \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

Then

$$X(t) = X_0 + \int_0^t \varphi_0(X, s)ds + \int_0^t \varphi_1(X, s)dw(s), \forall t \in [0, T]. \quad (26)$$

The non-classical part of EDS is the stochastic integral

$$\int_0^t \varphi_1(X, S)dw(s). \quad (27)$$

4. APPLICATION OF STOCHASTIC PROCESSES ON THERMODYNAMIC SYSTEMS

Thermodynamic systems adhere to several fundamental laws that govern energy and mass exchanges, as well as the transformations of the system's states. Here is an overview of the key laws of thermodynamics: The first law of thermodynamics states that the total energy of an isolated system remains constant. In other words, energy cannot be created or destroyed, only converted from one form to another. For a closed system, this law is expressed by the following equation:

$$du = q - c(dw(t)). \quad (28)$$

Such as

u : is the variation of the internal energy of the system, q represents the heat added to the system, and in other ways c is the work done by the system. dw : system perturbation under random circumstances denoted by the stochastic operator. In an open system, this law is extended to include mass fluxes, as mentioned earlier in the energy balance. The second law of thermodynamics states that the entropy of an isolated system can never decrease; it tends to increase until it reaches a maximum at equilibrium.

This law introduces the notion of irreversibility of natural processes. It can be formulated as follows:

$$\Delta C(t) > 0.$$

Where $\Delta C(t)$ is the change in the entropy of the system. The third law of thermodynamics states that the entropy of a perfect crystal at zero absolute temperature is exactly zero. This means that at this temperature

the particles of the crystal are in a state of perfect order. Mathematically, it can be expressed as:

$$C \rightarrow 0 \text{ and } X(t) \rightarrow 0.$$

4.1 APPLICATION FORMULATION OF THE ENERGY BALANCE

Open systems exchange energy and mass with surroundings, requiring an energy balance that accounts for heat, work, and mass flow. Where the system defined with the following equation

$$dX(t, q) = \theta(t) \{X(t, q) dt + \xi(t) X(t, q) dw(t)\}. \quad (29)$$

$X(t, q)$: is the total heat flux entering the system.

$\theta(t)$: is the net work done by the system.

$\xi(t)$: are the specific enthalpies of the incoming and outgoing mass flows.

$dw(t)$: System disruption.

Then, numerical solution will be approximate by works of Nabil LAICHE and all [12]

$$X(t) = \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(2-\gamma)} \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{X_j - X_{j-1}}{t_j - t_{j-1}} t_j \left\{ (t_n^\theta - t_{j-1}^\theta) - (t_n^\theta - t_j^\theta) \right\} \right) - \frac{1}{\xi_n \sqrt{\Delta t_n}}. \quad (30)$$

We assume the following neutron flux equation with fractional derivative of order 0.25, see [15]

$$\begin{cases} d^{0.25} X(t) = 0.5X(t) + dW(t) \\ 0 = t_0 < t_1 < t_2 = 1 \end{cases}. \quad (31)$$

Then,

$$X(t) = \frac{2^{0.25}}{\Gamma(3/2)} \sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{X_j - X_{j-1}}{t_j - t_{j-1}} t_j^{1-\alpha} \left\{ (1-t_{j-1}^{\sqrt{2}})^{0.5} - (1-t_j^{\sqrt{2}})^{0.5} \right\} - \frac{1}{\xi_n \sqrt{\Delta t_n}}. \quad (32)$$

The solution of a thermodynamic diffusion equation in nuclear physics usually involves the use of stochastic calculus to better model anomalous diffusion, where the standard diffusion equation may not be sufficient. Fractional diffusion equations introduce non-integer order derivatives, which can more accurately describe the heat transport properties in some complex situation.

5. DYNAMIC SYSTEM SAMPLES' MODELLING

Stochastic differential equations are essential for modeling thermodynamic systems with random fluctuations, especially in small systems like colloidal particles. Stochastic thermodynamics uses Langevin equations to describe dynamics, combining fluctuating entropy with energy balances, thus aligning classical thermodynamics with the behavior of mesoscopic systems.

5.1. PHYSICAL FORMULATION

Consider a stochastic equation modeling heat diffusion in a system or, as a basic model, the overdamped motion $X(t)$

$$X(t) = e^{-at} X(t-p)dt + De^{-bt} X(t-p)dW(t), p > 0. \quad (33)$$

$X(t)$ in physics represents the movement as a system operator, in this case a systematic force. e^{-at} and e^{-bt} are model coefficients, where D is the diffusion constant, and the mobility δ are related by the Einstein relation

$$D = T \delta. \quad (34)$$

Where T is the temperature of the surrounding medium with the Boltzmann relation, this relation is quite physical since in an overdamped system, the total force multiplied by the displacement corresponds to the dissipation. Integrated along a trajectory of given length, we obtain the expression

$$X(t) = e^{-at} X(t-p)dt + De^{-bt} X(t-p)dW(t), p > 0. \quad (35)$$

To approach the solutions of this first equation we have the stability conditions, according to the properties of the stochastic model we have

$$X(t-p) = \varphi(t)X(t). \quad (36)$$

So, the equation becomes by a recurring sequence [17]

$$X(t_{n+1}) = e^{-at_n} \varphi(t_n)X(t_n) + De^{-bt_n} \varphi(t_n)X(t_n)\varepsilon(t_n), p > 0. \quad (37)$$

So, the generalized solution according to Subba Rao [2]

$$X(t) = \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \left[\prod_{j=1}^l ((e^{-aj} + e^{-bj})\varepsilon(j)) \right] \varepsilon(l). \quad (38)$$

It is clear to confirm that this solution is convergent because tends towards a convergent geometric series with a basis $0 < r < 1$.

CONCLUSION

In thermodynamic systems, solution values for equations depend on specific system parameters and initial conditions. For instance, in an ideal gas, knowing the pressure, volume, and temperature allows the determination of the gas quantity. The first law of thermodynamics connects internal energy, heat added or removed, and work done by the system. The second law helps calculate entropy changes based on heat exchange and temperature. Gibbs free energy, indicating the energy available for work, depends on enthalpy,

entropy, and temperature. For out-of-equilibrium systems, such as particles affected by external forces and thermal noise, complex dynamic equations model the fluctuating trajectories of particles over time.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abbes, A., Ouannas, A., Shawagfeh, N., & Khennaoui, A. A. (2022). Incommensurate fractional discrete neural network: chaos and complexity. *The European Physical Journal Plus*, 137(2), 235.
- [2] Abu Hammad, M. M., Alkhateeb, R., Laiche, N., Ouannas, A., & Alshorm, S. (2024). Comparative Analysis of Bilinear Time Series Models with Time-Varying and Symmetric GARCH Coefficients: Estimation and Simulation. *Symmetry*, 16(5), 581.
- [3] Anh, P. T., Doan, T. S., & Huong, P. T. (2019). A variation of constant formula for Caputo fractional stochastic differential equations. *Statistics & Probability Letters*, 145, 351-358.
- [4] Ben Makhlof, A., & Nagy, A. M. (2020). Finite-time stability of linear Caputo-Katugampola fractional-order time delay systems. *Asian Journal of Control*, 22(1), 297-306.
- [5] Bibi, A., & Merahi, F. (2023). Estimating continuous-time bilinear process with moments method. *Nonlinear Studies*, 30(3).
- [6] Bibi, A., & Merahi, F. (2020). Yule-Walker type estimator of first-order time-varying periodic bilinear differential model for stochastic processes. *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods*, 49(16), 4046-4072.
- [7] Chakraborty, S. (2023). Deep Physics Corrector: A physics enhanced deep learning architecture for solving stochastic differential equations. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 479, 112004.

- [8] Chandra, S. K., & Bajpai, M. K. (2023). Efficient Machine Learning and Fractional Calculus Based Mathematical Model for Early COVID Prediction. *Human-Centric Intelligent Systems*, 3(4), 508-520.
- [9] Evans, L. C. (2012). An introduction to stochastic differential equations (Vol. 82). American Mathematical Soc.
- [10] Fallahgoul, H., Focardi, S., & Fabozzi, F. (2016). Fractional calculus and fractional processes with applications to financial economics: Theory and application. Academic Press.
- [11] Feshbach, H. (1992). Theoretical nuclear physics: nuclear reactions.
- [12] He, X., Wang, F., Li, W., & Sheng, D. (2022). Deep learning for efficient stochastic analysis with spatial variability. *Acta Geotechnica*, 17(4), 1031-1051.
- [13] Laiche, n., Gasmi, l., Vinoth, r., & Zeghdoudi, h. (2024). exploring novel approaches for estimating fractional stochastic processes through practical applications. *J. Appl. Math. & Informatics* Vol, 42(2), 223-235.
- [14] Merahi, Fateh, and Abdelouahab Bibi. "Evolutionary transfer functions solution for continuous {time bilinear stochastic processes with time-varying coefficients." *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods* 50.22 (2021): 5189-5214.
- [15] Miller, K. S. (1993). An Introduction to the Fractional Calculus and Fractional Differential Equations.
- [16] Nabil, Laiche, Gasmi Laid, and Zeghdoudi Halim. "New perspectives in space of COGARCH (1, 1) models with fractional derivative." *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)* 14.2 (2023): 866-876.
- [17] Sakthivel, R., Revathi, P., & Ren, Y. (2013). Existence of solutions for nonlinear fractional stochastic differential equations. *Nonlinear Analysis: Theory, Methods & Applications*, 81, 70-86.
- [18] Sibatov, R. T., & Uchaikin, V. V. (2009). Fractional differential approach to dispersive transport in semiconductors. *Physics-Uspeski*, 52(10), 1019.
- [19] Weidenmüller, H. A., & Mitchell, G. E. (2009). Random matrices and chaos in nuclear physics: Nuclear structure. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 81(2), 539.
- [20] Zeng, S., Baleanu, D., Bai, Y., & Wu, G. (2017). Fractional differential equations of Caputo–Katugampola type and numerical solutions. *Applied Mathematics and computation*, 315, 549-554.
- [21] Zhang, Z., & Karniadakis, G. E. (2017). Numerical methods for stochastic partial differential equations with white noise (Vol. 196). Cham: Springer.